

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEAKING SKILLS IN KOREAN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract The concept of "speech skills" as a part of oral competence, its structure represented by meaningful and pragmatic components is considered. Oral communication skills reflect the unique characteristics of the Korean language, namely, knowledge of cultural traditions, knowledge of social situations and social functions of communication, and nonverbal characteristics of oral communication in Korean. The purpose of this study is to show the specific aspects of this skill, which are different from other languages, based on the definitions given by experts to the oral speech of the Korean language. The tasks of the research are (1) to interpret based on the opinions of Korean linguists, to analyze the differences and similarities between oral speech and (2) the relationship of oral speech skills with other types of speech activity (3) was to show that it fulfills its main task for speaking, listening and reading. In our research, we used the research works of Korean scientists of oral communication skills. A Pragmatic component is represented by a complex of compensatory, perceptual and discursive abilities. Special attention is paid to the definition of discursive skill, discursive marker. Korean speech marks are highlighted. Methodical methods are offered for developing strategic speech competence and teaching oral communication in Korean.

Key words: strategic competence, discourse competence, strategic discourse competence, Korean language, oral communication, communicative maxim, compensatory skill, perceptual skill, discursive skill, discourse marker.

Introduction

The purpose of this article is to consider the structure of strategic speech competence as one of the components of communicative competence. A characteristic feature of the modern world is a person's constant participation in international communication. A foreign language serves as a means of forming a multicultural personality. Today, in accordance with the social order of society, teaching a foreign language, in particular, the Korean language, consists of "studying the socio-psychological features of language, thinking, speech communication activities, modeling and teaching communicative interaction situations"[1, 39]. The goal of teaching Korean language should be considered not only language competence, but also the formation of speech competence that corresponds to the ability to effectively perform certain functions in various communication situations using the target language based on the language [1, p. 93].

Local Korean methodologists have a serious research task to develop a Korean language teaching method that can teach Korean communication quickly and effectively in a short time, because the conditions of Korean language teaching in school and university are different from Korean language.

Accordingly, the urgency of activating the process of teaching the Korean language in schools and universities is clearly visible. In our opinion, one of the ways to solve the problem of preparing graduates for Korean language communication in a foreign language is the formation of strategic speech competence in the process of learning Korean language.

The formation of oral speech skills ensures "the implementation of a certain strategy by a person in the process of communication." According to the research of O. S. Issers, speech strategy represents "a set of speech actions aimed at achieving communicative goals" [3, p. 54].

Thus, oral communication skills are considered as the ability to organize speech interaction, in which communicators influence each other, implement communicative

goals and use language skills, adequate to speech situations. has a sociolinguistic character [4, 101].

The formation of oral speech skills is carried out in the paradigm of cooperation, in the form of interpersonal communication, "regardless of whether a certain result is intentionally or consciously planned." [3,56].

Accordingly, when considering the content of oral speech skills, it is necessary to take into account the characteristics of oral communication in a foreign language.

The structure of oral speech skills under consideration, in our opinion, consists of a set of knowledge, skills and a nomenclature of certain interactive speech skills: on the one hand, knowledge of the main normative principles that regulate the behavior of interlocutors, and the peculiarities of oral communication in a foreign language, in this case the Korean language, on the other hand, it is necessary to develop the communicative and interactive abilities of the participants of joint activities.

RESEARCH METHODS

In this study, data collection in Korean was based on academic articles written in Korean, research papers, and opinions of Korean linguists:

1. Which type of speech activity in Korean is better developed among students;
2. Which type of speaking skill exercise is most used in Korean language?

This skill cannot be developed without learning letters through sounds.

RESULTS AND CONSIDERATIONS

Oral speech skills: 1) the communicative contribution at each stage of the dialogue should be at the level required by the jointly accepted goal (direction) of this dialogue; 2) the speech should contain no less information than is necessary for the realization of the current goals of communication; 3) relationship and relevance [5, p. 17].

The specific characteristics of oral communication in Korean can be expressed by the following knowledge: 1) knowledge of cultural traditions (stereotypical

situations, manners, role characteristics); 2) knowledge of social situations and the social function of communication (functional and stylistic features (use of official, polite-formal, familiar and other communication styles), etiquette forms, specific features of address); 3) knowledge of non-verbal signs accepted in Korean culture.

Oral speech skills are determined by the following set of communicative and interactive skills necessary for the active work of all participants in joint activities: 1) complement your partners without repeating the above-mentioned points; 2) compliance with regulations; 3) encourage your partners and involve them in work.

At the same time, N.I. Almazova considers the following communicative skills to be part of oral speech skills: 1) avoiding complexity and length, adapting sentences to one's level of linguistic communication; 2) use of paraphrases when memory is weak; 3) use of synonyms, use [6, p. 16].

The following skills can be added to the presented nomenclature: 1) the ability to correctly formulate one's thoughts; 2) ability to use various linguistic tools correctly; 3) the ability to defend one's point of view [7, p. 67, 80, 86].

Thus, the above skills can be divided into the following groups:

1. Compensation skills: 1) turning to partners for help and explanation; 2) use of paraphrases when memory is weak; 3) use of synonyms; 5) checking the correctness of understanding; 6) use polite phrases and expressions to politely end the conversation; 7) to clarify the correct understanding of the interlocutor; 8) making new proposals in response to the interlocutors' proposals; 9) mitigation of rejection;

10) to continue the conversation and to understand the interlocutor, and then to realize the intention of the speech.

2. Perceptual skills: 1) taking turns; 2) encourage your partners and involve them in work; 3) use non-verbal gestures that show understanding and support; 4) show interest in what the interlocutor is talking about; 5) continue communication by responding positively to ratings.

3. Discursive skills: 1) forming one's thoughts correctly; 2) correct use of various linguistic tools; 3) to defend one's point of view; 4) introduce yourself; 5) put forward possible and counter-options; 6) draw a conclusion, 7) end the conversation.

In written speech, such indicators are defined as connectives, and in oral speech, they are defined as speech signs [7, p. 87]. V. E. Viktorova considers speech signs to be auxiliary communicative units - these are auxiliary verbal and non-verbal tools, with the help of which "communicators orient themselves in their speech in the process of interaction with the addressee, but do not contain factual information" [8, p. 21].

Fluency in Korean is the ultimate goal of almost every Korean language learner. Will your Korean speaking skills improve if you don't live in Korea? In this article, I will give you some tips to help you improve your Korean speaking skills. 1. Meet Korean friends

Having some language partners who can converse with you in Korean is very important. Living in Korea for a few months or a year is the best way to learn Korean, but it is not an easy task for everyone. But nowadays, with the rapid development of the Internet, it is not difficult to find some Korean friends who want to help you. You can find language exchange partners on Facebook groups, sites like Italki, or apps like Hellochat. If you can't find Korean-born friends, there are Korean-speaking people in every country and you should make friends with them.

2. Join Korean language learners

There are many communities of Korean learners on Facebook, Reddit, and elsewhere. You can also find language partners in these communities and communicate with them in Korean.

3. Read aloud

Read at least 10-20 Korean sentences a day. They can be from your textbooks, online newspapers, novels, or anything else. Always read them aloud and focus on

pronunciation. Reading aloud doesn't just tune your vocal cords to Korean sounds. Learn more in sync with your Korean sounds.

4. Speak and listen yourself
5. Start writing in Korean every day
6. Play a virtual role
7. Listen to Korean radio
8. Watch Korean TV shows
9. Don't be afraid to make mistakes

CONCLUSION

The signs of speech include introductory sentences, prepositional structures, introductory words, particles that primarily serve in oral speech and direct it to the listener.

The presented structure of oral speech skills in teaching the Korean language and the methodical methods described above will allow you to optimize the learning process, because it is necessary to quickly and effectively develop Korean speaking skills and abilities in a short period of time.

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